

THE ROLE OF CRAFTSMANSHIP IN ENHANCEMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVITY

Roila Yuldoshvoyevna Xaydarova

Technology teacher at school

№14 of Bostonliq district, Tashkent region

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10403199>

Abstract. *This article aims to study and teach the essence of our national craft, drought, to increase the interest of young people in this craft and bring it more in tune with the times.*

Keywords: *handicrafts, textiles, design, handicrafts, entrepreneurship, decoration.*

Today, when the reform of the continuous education system in independent Uzbekistan has begun to be reorganized in the process of education based on new educational standards, special attention is paid to the teacher's work and his pedagogical art. In our republic, great attention is paid to the education of the young generation, who are the creators of our future, especially to raising their general cultural, ideological-political, spiritual and intellectual potential, and raising them to become mature individuals in all respects. Our President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev.

The problem of preparing young people for work is the most important issue in our society, although its development is measured by the level of preparation of young people for life, work, and tomorrow. In a word, for the future of the new Uzbekistan, young people who have perfectly learned their specialty are extremely necessary. This puts great responsibilities on us young people. Our highly qualified personnel, our youth will create the future of our republic. Therefore, if every teacher, every specialist loves his profession, works on it regularly, is in search every minute, we can achieve the goal in front of us. Currently, attention is being paid more and more to folk art, which is taught in our republic and is our million-year-old heritage. If we fully take over the folk arts inherited from our ancestors, the problem of the need for raw materials imported from other republics will be solved by itself we will have.

The word Kurok comes from the word black-white. Because mostly black and white fabrics are widely used in dry sewing. Kuroq is the process of combining scraps and pieces of gauze of different colors and textures into one piece, holding and collecting small pieces, creating decorations, etc. Dry sewing was first created in England in the 11th century, and over the past centuries, it has reached our ancestors and has been transformed into our national craft and preserved to this day. Pillowcases, bedspreads, blankets, fans, bed sheets, tablecloths, sofa and table covers, carpets, clothes that embody the spirit of the time and day, as well as decorations and filling details for clothes are made by the drying method. can be prepared. From a very long time ago, our mothers sewed household items: blankets, pillows, blankets, rugs, clothes: napkins, caps, etc. Currently, various consumer goods, exportable raw materials, accessories, exhibitions are created using the dry method. They are being shown at various exhibitions. For example, yesterday at the "Bazar-Art" exhibition held in our capital, our national craftsmen used the drought to add charm to modern items. We can see these patterns in women's bags, caps, sheets of different sizes, and even shoes. In this way, the preparation of items is mainly done through economy. Our wise people have condemned wastefulness and not allowed it, and have prepared useful items from useless scraps.

Although all the kuroks have their own specific meaning and content according to their shape and decoration, in fact, at the root of all of them lies a noble goal that is unique to our people, and even this is our mother's in other words, "Let the people of our country share and fight, and let their children chase each other and always be in harmony." Therefore, examples of practical art created in the kurak method are not just objects, but also serve as a symbolic sign of the noble goals and wishes of our people. Currently, it is no exaggeration to say that the art of dry sewing is a universal art form. Because the items created using this art form are an integral part of the everyday life of many nations, and this art form shows the creativity and talent of the people of each nation.

Studying the art of dry sewing allows you to get to know the uniqueness of Uzbek folk craft schools, regional traditions and the taste of home craftsmen, to understand its place and development as a special artistic process in the development of modern folk art. serves to determine the contribution.

From the history of Uzbek folk art, the art of needlework shows that our people not only have an aesthetic taste, but also that they do not allow extravagance, are thrifty, and have a heart familiar with art. It is worth noting that every piece of dry art created by our people speaks of signs, ornaments, patterns and symbols. Because no part of the art samples is simple, every detail and appearance in them reflects the lifestyle, dreams, hopes and traditions of our people. It is natural for any master seamstress who works with gauze to have a desire to use the leftovers in the art room for what they need, without throwing them away. On the one hand, this shows the thriftiness and frugality characteristic of women, and on the other hand, it shows creativity and creativity. This will increase the interest in Uzbek folk art, shape the aesthetic taste, and develop manual dexterity.

Today, we have reached a time when fashion is combined with modern design. Even if we look at the modern clothes that breathe today, we can see patterns and decorations in them. has a unique appearance. This is another vivid example of the increasing attention to our national handicrafts today.

Dry connection methods:

The mill method - for this, first of all, 4 diagonally united squares are prepared from 2 triangles. Then these squares are 2, then all are combined. It is necessary to pay attention to color contrast.

Star method - First, a square is prepared for the center. This square can be assembled as a whole or from triangles as desired. Then the first and second views are completed and joined to the center. Then the third and fourth views are done and all the joins are combined into a rectangle or square.

American Square - A simple ruler can be used as a template to make these squares. Its length corresponds to all sides of the squares. It is not recommended to pre-cut the length of the strips. Their length should be determined after sewing.

A square within a square - First, the base square is sewn. Then 4 triangles are sewn along its four sides. The work continues in this way until the triangles are placed along the corners to form squares.

The striped method is considered one of the most common connecting methods, and when sewing in this method, there is almost no waste of stitches, and it differs from other methods in that it is easy to sew. There are many different ways to sew a garment with the striping method,

the striping is first gathered into square or triangular blocks and then made into a piece, or by joining them together as long ribbons and then forming a core into the piece. can be connected.

Russian square is a convenient way to create different compositions. In this method, the color image can be widely used. Because it is convenient to show brightly colored gashes in the central part of the block and in the outer corner parts. At the same time, it is possible to successfully use gauzes of ordinary colors. Even the most simple colored gauze is combined with other colors here.

The house or well method is a block assembled from striped tapes and shapes in drought. In the USA, this method is called a "wooden house". The symbolic meaning of the straw sewn in this way is a wooden house with a fire burning in the middle. The fire illuminates the house and creates shadows in the corners. Therefore, one side of the cut is sewn from bright colored cuts, and the other side is made from dark colored cuts.

In conclusion, we can say that our craftsmanship is our greatest wealth and pride. It is our duty to preserve it, polish it, and pass it on to the next generation without defects. For this purpose, we will work with all our energy in accordance with innovative ideas, using new techniques and technologies. It is not for nothing that it has been said since time immemorial that "wealth comes from craft, marriage brings beauty." We will build a new Uzbekistan with our hardworking people and craftsmen.

REFERENCES

1. Шойимова М.Р.ИСТОРИЯ БИСЕРА И БИСЕРНЫХ УКРАШЕНИЙ. "LXXV INTERNATIONAL CORRESPONDENCE SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY" 16.03.2022 yil. C-106-108.
<https://internationalconference.ru/images/PDF/2022/75/history-of-beads.pdf>
2. Муқимовна К. N. DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNICAL CREATIVITY OF STUDENTS WITH THE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES //European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2022. – Т. – С. 44-49.
3. Хамдамова Н. М. РАЗВИТИЕ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ ТЕХНИЧЕСКОГО ТВОРЧЕСТВА ОБУЧАЕМЫХ НА УРОКАХ ФИЗИКИ //The 2nd International scientific and practical conference "Results of modern scientific research and development"(May 2-4, 2021) Barca Academy Publishing, Madrid, Spain. 2021. 640 p. – 2021. – С. 361.
4. Хамдамова Н. М. РАЗВИТИЕ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ ТЕХНИЧЕСКОГО ТВОРЧЕСТВА УЧЕНИКОВ //The 2nd International scientific and practical conference "Results of modern scientific research and development"(May 2-4, 2021) Barca Academy Publishing, Madrid, Spain. 640 p. – 2021. – С. 357.